

The Effect Of The Constructivist Learning Model On Learning Some Types Of Basketball Shooting For First-Stage Students

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 17, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: June 24, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Basketball Shooting, Physical Education, Sports Sciences</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5027611</p>	<p><i>There is no doubt about scientific progress in the field of education and learning in physical education and sports sciences, and the choice of the optimal method of learning is the most influential factor in the progress and development of the level. The effect of constructivist learning on learning and developing shooting in its different types of basketball, and the researcher used the experimental method with two experimental and control groups. The sample of the research was from the first stage students in the College of Physical Education and Sports Sciences at the University of Basra, which numbered 40 students, and the results were statistically processed, after presentation and discussion. One of the most important conclusions of the research was that constructivist learning had a clear impact on the progress and development of the skills level under research, and the researcher recommended the necessity of designing educational programs based on constructivist learning that suit different age stages.</i></p>

Introduction

Human learning is the result of arousal that starts from a sense of a problem imposed by the conditions and requirements of reality, and ends with the formation of an experience that responds and takes into account the principles of this reality, and through it the individual seeks to acquire and acquire knowledge, and a cumulative addition to new experiences. (5:125), and despite the existence of the ability to learn in human beings, this ability is different and varied from one individual to another, and this disparity is a necessity for the diversity of human activity and achieving its integration, as the diversity of abilities is a link and interconnection between the human being and his brother The constructivist learning method is one of the methods of constructivist theory that relies on the learner's prior knowledge to obtain dimensional knowledge through understanding and awareness resulting from the interaction between prior and subsequent knowledge that leads to the stability of this awareness through practice after modifying perceptions and prior knowledge to accommodate new experiences. It helps learners to build their scientific concepts and knowledge (306:1). The constructivist learning strategy is based on four stages: advocacy, exploration, proposing solutions and explanations, and finally taking action. The advocacy phase depends on attracting the learners' attention and their participation in the activity by presenting some Pictures and asking questions that invite thinking provided that this activity is linked to previous information and experiences they have with interest in encouraging and motivating, while the exploration stage challenges the abilities of the learners to try to reach the answers to the questions through observation, measurement and experimentation, and problems are solved by collecting information and implementing the activity, and the teacher guides and encourages with Dialogue and information exchange, then comes the stage of proposing solutions and explanations, and here the wrong concepts are modified The stage of taking action is the stage of application, and the teacher must give the learners sufficient time to apply what they have learned during their cooperation, and they may encounter new information that leads to a new invitation (5:6). The stage of learning the basic principles is the most difficult stage of learning to raise the skill level, as it is the ladder to rise towards proficiency and mastery. Therefore, the importance of constructivist learning appears in that it is based on correcting wrong knowledge and building and acquiring the correct knowledge on which sound skill performance is built. The accumulation of knowledge and information is not important. When compared with the organization of this knowledge, if it is organized, it is fixed and solid, and this facilitates the learning process and reduces its time.

Research problem

It is no secret that the process of thinking, which is a deliberate exploration of experience in order to reach the goal, is important in the life of the individual, and more importantly is learning the ways of thinking, in other words, paying attention to the learning outcomes and memorizing them is not first and more important than paying attention to how to reach these outcomes. Delivering knowledge and information to the learner is the most successful way for the learner to realize and understand what is required of him in the educational process,

and accordingly it is noticeable that the learner in his first stage of learning makes many mistakes when applying the required skill, so he does what he should not do, and does not do what he should do, and this is due to the lack of awareness and perception of the skill in its details and stages in a correct and accurate manner, which causes these errors to fall. Building knowledge and information correctly at the beginning of learning constitutes the main factor in performing the skill and avoids many performance errors. Hence, the research problem is summarized in the following question: Is constructivist learning and cognitive assessment is effective in learning some types of shooting in basketball with few performance errors?

Research aims

Objective of research on exposure P on

1. The effectiveness of constructivist learning in learning to shoot from stability (free throw) in basketball for first-year students in the College of Physical Education and Sports Sciences - University of Basra.
2. The effectiveness of constructivist learning in learning peaceful shooting in basketball for first-year students in the College of Physical Education and Sports Sciences - University of Basra.
3. The effectiveness of constructivist learning in learning to shoot from jumping in basketball for first-year students in the College of Physical Education and Sports Sciences - University of Basra.

Search fields m

1. The human field: first-year students in the College of Physical Education and Sports Sciences - Basra University School for the year 2018-2019.
2. Time range: from 4/11/2018 to 19/12/2018.
3. 3- Spatial domain: Hall of the College of Physical Education and Sports Sciences - University of Basra.

Research procedures and field procedures

Research Methodology

To suit the nature of the research, the method was experimental for two groups, a control group and the other experimental.

Research community and sample

The research community is the students of the first stage in the College of Physical Education and Sports Sciences - University of Basra for the academic year 2018-2019 and from 120 students and a selected sample of them and from 40 students who were named in the first and second control groups by the pre and post test, and the number of each of them is 20 students after excluding the absent students. Study participants were not statistical.

Data collection methods

The researcher used the following Technology

1. The free throw test (264:3)
2. The scoring test by jumping to the left of the free-throw line and then moving a semi-circle to the middle and right (258:3)
3. The peaceful scoring test in front of the target from a distance of 5 meters within 15 seconds (280:3)

Tools and devices used in research

-computer - basketball court - stopwatch - registration form - whistle - chalk - cones - legal basketball - metric tape - tape length 1 meter.

Exploration experience

The researcher conducted an empirical test on a group of (10) students from the research community and outside the main sample on 10/28/2018.

Pretest

The tribal research test was conducted on the two groups (experimental and control) of a pony for sand shooting, jumping and peaceful correction in basketball on 10/10/2018 in the hall of the College of Physical Education and Sports Sciences at the University of Riyadh. Basra. .

The application of the constructivist learning model

The NP-y program is based on constructivist learning for a period of (45) days and by two pilot units per week, each unit (90) min. The experimental group, and the program according to the stages of the learning model Building A Four: The call stage, which aims to attract the attention of the learners, attract them and engage them in the activity by motivating them On new knowledge and information, such as asking some questions that require thinking, posing some problems that raise them intellectually, and the exploration stage. Which focuses on the learner in particular and aims to reach an answer to the questions and problems raised in the previous stage. By discussing cooperating groups, as a method of brainstorming, observing phenomena, interpreting the stage and proposing solutions, all of this brings the learner to concepts and knowledge to interpret results, answers and solutions, and T is the comparison and differentiation among them, discussed and criticized in order to adopt new cognitive explanations, and here the role of the teacher emerges In organizing ideas and information for learners, the stage of taking action. In this stage, concepts and information are transferred to situations of learning and application through activities.

Post Test

After completing the application of the program for the control and experimental groups, the research conducted a dimensional test of free throw shooting, jumping and peaceful correction in basketball on 12/12/2018.

Presentation of results and discussion

Table (1) Pre and post test results for the control group

Indication level	Values(T)	telemetry		Tribal measurement		measuring unit	the exams
		$\pm p$	s-	$\pm p$	s-		
D	1.45	0.87	9.15	1.22	8.85	Degree	free throw
D	3.45	0.71	12.25	1.37	11.00	Degree	Shooting from jump
D	1.16	0.61	2.80	0.68	2.60	Degree	Peaceful shooting

Table(2) the results of the pre and post tests for the experimental group

Indication level	Values(T)	telemetry		Tribal measurement		measuring unit	the exams
		$\pm p$	s-	$\pm p$	s-		
D	9.79	1.05	11.80	1.28	9.20	Degree	free throw
D	90.7	1.36	14.35	57.1	50.11	Degree	Shooting from jump
D	4.66	67.0	3.85	87.0	65.2	Degree	Peaceful shooting

Table(3) the results of the two post -tests for the experimental and control groups

Indication level	Values(T)	experimental group		control group		Alone measurement	the exams
		$\pm p$	s-	$\pm p$	s-		
D	8.64	1.05	11.80	0.87	9.15	Degree	free throw
D	99.6	0.71	14.35	1.13	12.25	Degree	Shooting from jump
D	5.15	0.67	3.85	0.61	2.80	Degree	Peaceful shooting

Discuss the Results

It is clear from Table No. (1), Table No. (2) And Table No. (3) That there are statistically significant differences between the pre and post tests of the control group, and between the pre and post tests of the control group. The control group. The experimental group and between the two post tests of the control and experimental group as shown in Table (3) the arithmetic mean in the experimental group for the skill of free throwing (11.80) with a standard deviation of (1.05). While the arithmetic mean in the control group was (9.15) with a standard deviation (0.87), and the arithmetic mean in the experimental group for the skill of jumping shooting (14.35) with a standard deviation (0.71). While the arithmetic mean in the control group was (12.25) and the standard deviation (1.13) and the arithmetic mean in the experimental group for the skill of ladder correction was (3.85) with the standard deviation (0.67), while the arithmetic mean of the experimental group was. As for the experimental group for the skill of correcting the ladder, it was (3.85) and the standard deviation was (0.67). The control group was (2.80) and the standard deviation n (0.61), and the difference in the experimental group was used as a result of an educational program based on the structural theory that relies on the learner's tribal knowledge to collect the subsequent knowledge through understanding. And the cognition outputs due to the Eli wind between the identifier Tin and before it, in turn, leads to the stability of cognition through practice after modifying the cognition experience and previous knowledge to accommodate the new knowledge, the education program was based on more than one stage, support, exploration, interpretation, problem solving and decision-making only, and as a result these stages raise interest and interest among The learner as the educational message is developed to be learned in the form of questions and stimuli that correspond to these stages to reach the understanding and awareness that facilitates the implementation of the performance skills correctly, and this was confirmed by Abdus Salam Mustafa and KojakHarKojak (30:4): Their desire and presence to work and motivate them to know the correct performance and the skill of the best performance. (17:2) Constructive learning depends in its application on group work through discussion and asking questions, and this helps in reaching the answer, correct perception and accurate knowledge. Constructive learning is not just a transfer of information from one person to another; it is a process of building and reconstructing knowledge and perception. And knowledge that is built in the mind and is based on tribal knowledge, and here the role of the teacher in providing an educational environment between the difference between current experiences and new experiences acquired by learners emerges. Structuring the learner in order to reach understanding.

Conclusions

Among the most important conclusions reached by the researcher:

1. Constructive learning had a clear impact on the progress and development of the skills level under study.
2. Constructive learning made a positive contribution to gaining knowledge and awareness.

Recommendations

The researchers recommend the following:

1. The necessity of using constructivist learning to learn and develop basic skills.
2. The necessity of designing educational programs based on constructivist learning to suit different age groups.

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